

Impact of Generative Artificial Intelligence on Knowledge Management in Software Engineering: A Systematic Mapping Study

Table 1: List of selected studies.

ID	Reference	Title	Year	Event Type
S1	[1]	Cypress Copilot: Development of an AI Assistant for Boosting Productivity and Transforming Web Application Testing	2025	Article
S2	[2]	Early Results of an AI Multiagent System for Requirements Elicitation and Analysis	2025	Conference paper
S3	[3]	Automatic Library Migration Using Large Language Models: First Results	2024	Conference paper
S4	[4]	Turning Low-Code Development Platforms into True No-Code with LLMs	2024	Conference paper
S5	[5]	Emergence of A Novel Domain Expert: A Generative AI-based Framework for Software Function Point Analysis	2024	Conference paper
S6	[6]	Towards Generating Measurable Artifact Models from Standards in Regulated Domains	2025	Conference paper
S7	[7]	Prompting GPT-4 to Support Automatic Safety Case Generation	2024	Article
S8	[8]	Service-Oriented Requirements Elicitation Through Systematic Questionnaire Design: A Problem-Driven GenAI Approach	2025	Conference paper
S9	[9]	Calico: Automated Knowledge Calibration and Diagnosis for Elevating AI Mastery in Code Tasks	2024	Conference paper
S10	[10]	PTB-FLA Development Paradigm Adaptation for ChatGPT	2024	Article
S11	[11]	AI-Driven Refactoring: A Pipeline for Identifying and Correcting Data Clumps in Git Repositories	2024	Article
S12	[12]	Enhancing Security in Industrial Application Development: Case Study on Self-Generating Artificial Intelligence Tools	2024	Article
S13	[13]	Self-Collaboration Code Generation via ChatGPT	2024	Article
S14	[14]	BHRAMARI: Bug driven highly reusable automated model for automated test bed generation and integration	2024	Article
S15	[15]	Exploring ChatGPT's code refactoring capabilities: An empirical study	2024	Article
S16	[16]	X-Lifecycle Learning for Cloud Incident Management using LLMs	2024	Conference paper
S17	[17]	Evaluating Human-AI Partnership for LLM-based Code Migration	2024	Conference paper
S18	[18]	Research on Computer Intelligent ChatGPT Natural Language Processing System Based on Scientific Knowledge Graph	2024	Conference paper
S19	[19]	Chain of Targeted Verification Questions to Improve the Reliability of Code Generated by LLMs	2024	Conference paper
S20	[20]	No Need to Lift a Finger Anymore? Assessing the Quality of Code Generation by ChatGPT	2024	Article
S21	[21]	Human-AI Collaboration in Software Engineering: Lessons Learned from a Hands-On Workshop	2024	Conference paper
S22	[22]	Lessons from Building StackSpot AI: A Contextualized AI Coding Assistant	2024	Conference paper
S23	[23]	Using GitHub Copilot for Test Generation in Python: An Empirical Study	2024	Conference paper
S24	[24]	Commit Message Generation via ChatGPT: How Far Are We?	2024	Conference paper

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ID	Reference	Title	Year	Event Type
S25	[25]	Transforming Software Development: A Study on the Integration of Multi-Agent Systems and Large Language Models for Automatic Code Generation	2024	Conference paper
S26	[26]	Self-healing automation testing with Selenium and ChatGPT API integration to improve the efficiency of the maintenance	2024	Conference paper
S27	[27]	Java coding using artificial intelligence	2024	Article
S28	[28]	Developing a Llama-Based Chatbot for CI/CD Question Answering: A Case Study at Ericsson	2024	Conference paper
S29	[29]	Automating Software Documentation: Employing LLMs for Precise Use Case Description	2024	Conference paper
S30	[30]	Can Developers Prompt? A Controlled Experiment for Code Documentation Generation	2024	Conference paper
S31	[31]	TESTING METHODOLOGY FOR DEVS MODELS IN CAD-MIUM	2024	Conference paper
S32	[32]	Enhancing Software Engineering with AI: Key Insights from ChatGPT	2024	Conference paper
S33	[33]	DiCE: Distributed Code Generation and Execution	2024	Conference paper
S34	[34]	Automatic Service Composition Agent Based on Large Model	2024	Conference paper
S35	[35]	An Innovated Microservices Identification Approach Based on Database and Source Code Analysis	2024	Conference paper
S36	[36]	A Software Bug Fixing Approach Based on Knowledge-Enhanced Large Language Models	2024	Conference paper
S37	[37]	A Hybrid Framework for COSMIC Measurement: Combining Large Language Models with a Rule-Based System	2024	Conference paper
S38	[38]	SE Factual Knowledge in Frozen Giant Code Model: A Study on FQN and Its Retrieval	2024	Article
S39	[39]	Assessing GitHub Copilot in Solidity Development: Capabilities, Testing, and Bug Fixing	2024	Article
S40	[40]	Low-Code/No-Code Meets GenAI: A New Era in Product Development	2024	Conference paper
S41	[41]	Developer Behaviors in Validating and Repairing LLM-Generated Code Using IDE and Eye Tracking	2024	Conference paper
S42	[42]	The Impact of GitHub Copilot on Developer Productivity From a Software Engineering Body of Knowledge Perspective	2024	Conference paper
S43	[43]	Using Large Language Models to Support Software Engineering Documentation in Waterfall Life Cycles: Are We There Yet?	2024	Conference paper
S44	[44]	GiottoBugFixer: an effective and scalable easy-to-use framework for fixing software issues in a DevOps pipeline	2024	Conference paper
S45	[45]	Value-Based Adoption of ChatGPT in Agile Software Development: A Survey Study of Nordic Software Experts	2024	Book chapter
S46	[46]	From Natural Language to Web Applications: Using Large Language Models for Model-Driven Software Engineering	2024	Conference paper
S47	[47]	How to Refactor this Code? An Exploratory Study on Developer-ChatGPT Refactoring Conversations	2024	Conference paper
S48	[48]	Deriving Domain Models From User Stories: Human vs. Machines	2024	Conference paper
S49	[49]	Java Web Programming with ChatGPT	2024	Conference paper
S50	[50]	CODING WITH AI AS AN ASSISTANT: CAN AI GENERATE CONCISE COMPUTER CODE?	2024	Article
S51	[51]	Requirements are All You Need: From Requirements to Code with LLMs	2024	Conference paper
S52	[52]	Does Generative AI Generate Smells Related to Container Orchestration?: An Exploratory Study with Kubernetes Manifests	2024	Conference paper
S53	[53]	Enhancing Large Language Models in Coding Through Multi-Perspective Self-Consistency	2024	Conference paper
S54	[54]	AI-Driven Testing: Unleashing Autonomous Systems for Superior Software Quality Using Generative AI	2024	Conference paper
S55	[55]	Advancing Requirements Engineering Through Generative AI: Assessing the Role of LLMs	2024	Book chapter

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ID	Reference	Title	Year	Event Type
S56	[56]	A new approach for automatic test case generation from use case diagram using LLMs and prompt engineering	2024	Conference paper
S57	[57]	LLMs in Web Development: Evaluating LLM-Generated PHP Code Unveiling Vulnerabilities and Limitations	2024	Conference paper
S58	[58]	Beyond Agile: NLP-Driven Quality Attributes Retrieval Using ChatGPT in Software Development Strategies		
S59	[59]	Agile Project Management Using Large Language Models	2024	Conference paper
S60	[60]	Generative Artificial Intelligence for Test-Driven Development: GAI4-TDD	2024	Conference paper
S61	[61]	State of Practice: LLMs in Software Engineering and Software Architecture	2024	Conference paper
S62	[62]	Conversational Assistants for Software Development: Integration, Traceability and Coordination	2024	Conference paper
S63	[63]	The role of library versions in Developer-ChatGPT conversations	2024	Conference paper
S64	[64]	Unveiling ChatGPT's Usage in Open Source Projects: A Mining-based Study	2024	Conference paper
S65	[65]	Can ChatGPT support software verification?	2024	Conference paper
S66	[66]	Quality Assessment of ChatGPT Generated Code and their Use by Developers	2024	Conference paper
S67	[67]	Requirements Verification Through the Analysis of Source Code by Large Language Models	2024	Conference paper
S68	[68]	A Quantitative Analysis of Quality and Consistency in AI-generated Code	2024	Conference paper
S69	[69]	An Approach for Rapid Source Code Development Based on ChatGPT and Prompt Engineering	2024	Article
S70	[70]	Improving Source Code with Assistance from AI - A Pilot Case Study with ChatGPT	2024	Conference paper
S71	[71]	Generative AI to Generate Test Data Generators	2024	Article
S72	[72]	HDLGen-ChatGPT Case Study: RISC-V Processor VHDL and Verilog Model, Testbench and EDA Project Generation	2023	Conference paper
S73	[73]	On Programming Variability with Large Language Model-based Assistant	2023	Conference paper
S74	[74]	Are Prompt Engineering and TODO Comments Friends or Foes? An Evaluation on GitHub Copilot	2024	Conference paper
S75	[75]	The Potential Use of ChatGPT for Debugging and Bug Fixing	2023	Article
S76	[76]	An Empirical Understanding of Code Clone Detection by ChatGPT	2023	Conference paper
S77	[77]	From Manual to Automatic: The Evolution of Test Case Generation Methods and the Role of GitHub Copilot	2023	Conference paper
S78	[78]	Git Merge Conflict Resolution Leveraging Strategy Classification and LLM	2023	Conference paper
S79	[79]	Digital Rubber Duck: Leveraging Large Language Models for Extreme Programming	2023	Conference paper
S80	[80]	ChatGPT in IoT Systems: Arduino Case Studies	2023	Conference paper
S81	[81]	An Approach for Software Development Effort Estimation Using ChatGPT	2023	Conference paper
S82	[82]	A Self-Iteration Code Generation Method Based on Large Language Models	2023	Conference paper
S83	[83]	An Evaluation of the Effectiveness of OpenAI's ChatGPT for Automated Python Program Bug Fixing using QuixBugs	2023	Conference paper
S84	[84]	Practices and Challenges of Using GitHub Copilot: An Empirical Study	2023	Conference paper
S85	[85]	You Augment Me: Exploring ChatGPT-based Data Augmentation for Semantic Code Search	2023	Conference paper
S86	[86]	On the Use of ChatGPT to Support Agile Software Development	2023	Conference paper
S87	[87]	An Analysis of the Automatic Bug Fixing Performance of ChatGPT	2023	Conference paper
S88	[88]	ECHO: An Approach to Enhance Use Case Quality Exploiting Large Language Models	2023	Conference paper

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ID	Reference	Title	Year	Event Type
S89	[89]	Nuances are the Key: Unlocking ChatGPT to Find Failure-Inducing Tests with Differential Prompting	2023	Conference paper
S90	[90]	Unveiling insights in source code defect prediction using ChatGPT: moving beyond predictive metrics	2023	Conference paper
S91	[91]	On the Robustness of Code Generation Techniques: An Empirical Study on GitHub Copilot	2023	Conference paper
S92	[92]	Investigating Explainability of Generative AI for Code through Scenario-based Design	2022	Conference paper
S93	[93]	Is GitHub Copilot a Substitute for Human Pair-programming? An Empirical Study	2022	Conference paper
S94	[94]	Zero-shot Prompting for Code Complexity Prediction Using GitHub Copilot	2023	Conference paper
S95	[95]	Taking Flight with Copilot	2022	Article
S96	[96]	The Potential of Artificial Intelligence as a Method of Software Developer’s Productivity Improvement	2022	Conference paper
S97	[97]	How Data Scientists Improve Generated Code Documentation in Jupyter Notebooks	2021	Conference paper

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